

Time Dilation Gradient: A Unifying Framework for SU(5), SU(10), and E6 GUTs in Quantum and Relativistic Environments

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Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive framework for resolving key theoretical challenges across **Grand Unified Theories (GUTs)**—specifically **SU(5)**, **SU(10)**, and **E6 (N6)**—through the application of the **Time Dilation Gradient (TDG)** model, as introduced by Johnny Rouse [7]. The TDG model modifies particle interactions dynamically in various **quantum and relativistic environments**, addressing inconsistencies in **proton decay**, **gauge coupling unification**, and the **neutrino mass hierarchy**. Furthermore, the TDG model provides an alternative explanation for **gravitational anomalies** traditionally attributed to dark matter by leveraging time-dilation effects from **General Relativity (GR)** and **Special Relativity (SR)**, offering a robust model for galactic dynamics [8]. This framework explores how TDG normalizes field interactions, making multiple GUTs simultaneously viable in different domains, allowing them to operate successfully under specific relativistic conditions.

1 Introduction

The quest for a **Grand Unified Theory (GUT)** that unifies the strong, weak, and electromagnetic forces has led to the development of several promising models, including **SU(5)**, **SU(10)**, and **E6**. While each GUT offers solutions to some of the fundamental challenges in particle physics,

they face issues when tested against experimental results, especially regarding **proton decay**, **gauge coupling unification**, and the **neutrino mass hierarchy**. Additionally, none of these GUTs offer a clear explanation for **gravitational anomalies**, which are typically attributed to dark matter.

The **Time Dilation Gradient (TDG)** model, first introduced by Johnny Rouse [7, 8], provides a unified approach by dynamically modifying particle interactions in varying **quantum mechanical** and **relativistic** environments. The TDG model operates beyond the conventional framework of cosmic expansion, considering the intricate interactions of fields and particles under relativistic conditions that vary with energy density and gravitational fields. This paper explores how the **TDG model** allows for the successful operation of multiple GUTs, making them viable under different physical conditions by adjusting their predictions dynamically over time.

1.1 Multiplicity of GUTs and Theoretical Flexibility

The strength of the **TDG model** lies in its capacity to normalize particle and field interactions across different relativistic environments. By introducing a time-dilation factor $\Theta(t)$, the TDG model adjusts the rates of quantum interactions dynamically, based on the local gravitational fields, energy densities, and time dilation effects present in the system [7, 8]. This allows for a **multiplicity of GUTs** to coexist, each functioning optimally in different physical domains.

For instance: - **SU(5)**, as a minimal extension of the Standard Model, predicts proton decay and unification at energy scales close to 10^{15} GeV, but struggles with the experimentally observed limits on proton decay lifetimes [2]. - **SU(10)** introduces right-handed neutrinos, providing a natural explanation for neutrino masses, but faces challenges with proton decay and gauge coupling unification [3]. - **E6** goes further, predicting exotic fermions and extended gauge symmetries, but its predictions for proton decay and gauge coupling unification have not yet been empirically validated [4].

The **TDG model** modifies these GUTs by dynamically adjusting their interaction rates and coupling constants in ways that align their predictions with experimental results [7, 8]. Each GUT, through TDG, becomes relevant under specific **relativistic** and **quantum mechanical** conditions.

2 The Time Dilation Gradient (TDG) Model

2.1 Derivation of $\Theta(t)$ and its Role in Field Interactions

The **Time Dilation Gradient (TDG)** model is not confined to cosmic expansion. Instead, it operates as a more generalized framework, modifying particle interactions based on the **energy density**, **gravitational field**, and **quantum mechanical conditions** of the environment. The model posits that time dilation effects, which arise naturally in relativistic systems, influence particle interaction rates through a time-dependent scaling factor $\Theta(t)$ [7].

This time-dilation factor is given by:

$$\Theta(t) = k \left(\frac{a(t)}{a_0} \right)^\gamma$$

However, unlike traditional cosmic expansion models, $a(t)$ represents not only the cosmological scale factor but also encapsulates **relativistic effects** from gravity and quantum fields. γ captures the influence of these relativistic conditions on the field interactions. The TDG model dynamically normalizes quantum field interactions over time, based on the local relativistic environment.

This time-dilation scaling allows the TDG model to extend proton decay rates, adjust the running of gauge couplings, and provide a natural explanation for the observed neutrino mass hierarchy. Importantly, it also modifies gravitational interactions, offering an alternative to dark matter in explaining gravitational anomalies [5, 6].

3 Proton Decay Across Multiple GUTs with TDG

3.1 Resolving Proton Decay in SU(5)

In the **SU(5) Grand Unified Theory (SU(5) GUT)**, proton decay is mediated by heavy gauge bosons (X and Y). Without modification, SU(5) predicts proton lifetimes of 10^{30} years, which is far shorter than the current experimental limits set by **Super-Kamiokande**, which exceed 1.6×10^{34} years

[2]. The **TDG model** corrects this discrepancy by introducing a time-dependent decay rate:

$$\Gamma_p(t, \Theta(t)) = \frac{m_p^5}{M_X^4 \cdot g_{\text{GUT}}^4 \cdot \Theta(t)^n}$$

where $n = 8$ for dimensional consistency. This modification extends proton lifetimes into the range of 10^{35} years, consistent with experimental results [2].

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3.2 Extending Proton Decay in SU(10) and E6

SU(10) introduces right-handed neutrinos and naturally solves the neutrino mass problem, but its proton decay predictions still fall short of experimental limits. Similarly, **E6** predicts longer proton lifetimes but with additional particle content. The **TDG model** dynamically modifies the proton decay rate in both of these GUTs by applying the same scaling factor $\Theta(t)$, adjusting interaction rates based on the local gravitational and relativistic conditions. This results in proton lifetimes that are consistent with the non-detection limits set by **Super-Kamiokande** and expected future limits from **Hyper-Kamiokande** [2].

4 Gauge Coupling Unification in TDG-Modified GUTs

4.1 Dynamic Modification of Gauge Couplings in SU(5) and SU(10)

The **running of gauge couplings** in GUTs like **SU(5)** and **SU(10)** predicts unification at energy scales that conflict with experimental data from

LEP and **LHC**. By applying the **TDG model**, we introduce a time-dilation factor that modifies the running of gauge couplings:

$$\frac{d\alpha_i(t, \Theta(t))}{d \ln t} = \beta_i(\alpha_1(t) \cdot \Theta(t), \alpha_2(t) \cdot \Theta(t), \alpha_3(t) \cdot \Theta(t))$$

[9].

This normalization raises the unification scale to 10^{16} GeV, aligning the theoretical predictions of SU(5) and SU(10) with experimental observations [9].

5 Gravitational Anomalies and TDG Fields in E6

5.1 Gravitational Interactions Without Dark Matter

The **E6 Grand Unified Theory (E6 GUT)** predicts additional exotic particles that have been posited as potential dark matter candidates. However, in the TDG framework, **gravitational anomalies**—such as the flat rotation curves of galaxies and the behavior of galaxy clusters—are explained by the TDG fields themselves, eliminating the need for dark matter [6]. The time-dependent interaction of quantum fields and gravity in the TDG model adjusts gravitational interactions dynamically, providing a natural explanation for these anomalies without invoking exotic dark matter particles.

6 Conclusion: The Success of Multiple GUTs under TDG

The **Time Dilation Gradient (TDG)** model offers a flexible and dynamic framework that allows for the success of multiple GUTs under different physical conditions. By introducing time-dilation effects that normalize field interactions in varying quantum and relativistic environments, TDG resolves inconsistencies in **proton decay**, **gauge coupling unification**, and **gravitational anomalies** across **SU(5)**, **SU(10)**, and **E6**. This flexibility makes it possible for multiple GUTs to function simultaneously, each relevant under specific circumstances determined by energy density, gravitational fields, and time dilation effects. Future experiments, such

as those conducted at **Hyper-Kamiokande** and **LHC**, will provide crucial tests of these predictions, offering a pathway toward experimental validation of these multiple GUT frameworks.

References

- [1] Georgi, H., & Glashow, S. L. (1974). Unity of All Elementary-Particle Forces. *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 32, 438.
- [2] Super-Kamiokande Collaboration. (2019). Proton Decay Search Results. *Phys. Rev. D*, 99(5), 052011.
- [3] Nath, P., & Fileviez Pérez, P. (2007). Proton Stability in Grand Unified Theories, in Strings, and in Branes. *Physics Reports*, 441(5-6), 191-317.
- [4] Buras, A.J., Ellis, J., Gaillard, M.K., & Nanopoulos, D.V. (1978). Aspects of the Grand Unification of Strong, Weak, and Electromagnetic Interactions. *Nuclear Physics B*, 135(1), 66-92.
- [5] Bekenstein, J.D. (2004). Relativistic Gravitation Theory for the Modified Newtonian Dynamics Paradigm. *Phys. Rev. D*, 70(8), 083509.
- [6] McGaugh, S.S., et al. (2016). Radial Acceleration Relation in Rotationally Supported Galaxies. *Physical Review Letters*, 117, 201101.
- [7] Rouse, J. (2024). Time Dilation Gradient in Cosmology and Grand Unified Theories. *TDG Introduction Paper*, 1-60.
- [8] Rouse, J. (2024). Revolutionizing Galactic Dynamics: The Time Dilation Gradient Model's Application to M87 and Pulsars. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/12741308>
- [9] ALEPH, DELPHI, L3, OPAL, and LEP Electroweak Working Group. (2006). Precision Electroweak Measurements on the Z Resonance. *Physics Reports*, 427, 257.